

Levelling Up for Nature: Pathways of Engagement with Green Messages in Games

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Abstract—Digital games have become potent platforms for environmental messaging, capable of influencing beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours. This paper explores how players engage with green content embedded within game environments, using mixed-method data from the GREAT Project with more than 181,000 anonymised gameplay sessions. This research analysed cognitive, affective and behavioural responses to in-game environmental messaging and identified key pathways that lead to sustained pro-environmental actions using PCA and K-Means clustering analysis, by which varying types of user were identified from casual to deeply engaged players. The engagement questions were grouped into three categories: narrative frame, behavioural pledges, and social reflection. Our findings showed that 68% of the players participated in at least one green-themed pledge, which indicates a strong sensitivity to environmental content, informing a multilayered engagement model that supports both player experience and environmental literacy known as a 5-pathway green engagement model (5-PGEM), supporting the hypothesis that green messages, when embedded in games, can significantly shape eco-friendly actions.

Index Terms—Green messaging, in-Game, GREAT PROJECT, Behaviours, Pro-environmental Actions, eco-friendly, Empathy, Engagement, PCA, K-Means.

I. INTRODUCTION

Gaming has evolved into a cultural and behavioural ecosystem with enormous reach. With more than 3 billion players worldwide, it presents a novel opportunity for ecological communication. The GREAT Project and similar initiatives demonstrate that embedding climate narratives in games can catalyse real-world behaviour change [1]. This paper seeks to map how players interact with green messages across varying game genres and design formats, with a focus on the mechanisms that transform exposure into action. The inflation of the environmental crisis calls for fresh innovative strategies to teach people about the planet and raise awareness,

spanning across different cultures and communities. Although traditional environmental communication approaches are still valuable, they often struggle to engage younger audiences and sustain attention in an increasingly digital world [2]. Despite a global gaming population exceeding 3 billion, the potential of video games as a medium for environmental storytelling remains significantly underexplored and underutilised in scholarly and practical contexts. Contemporary communication with the environment has faced several critical problems, for instance, message fatigue among audiences battered with climate change warnings and carbon footprints, inadequate engagement with the conventional educational pattern, and difficulty in converting environmental awareness into a change in behaviour [3]. Bridging the distance between the urgency of environmental challenges and the ineffectiveness of traditional communication methods has pushed curiosity into investigating alternative ways for humans to engage with the environment empathically as shown in Fig 1. Research shows that games have demonstrated strength in education [4], social awareness, and health promotion, but their specific mechanisms for transferring environmental messages that inspire and translate to pro-environmental attitudes have not been properly understood.

A. The specific objectives include;

- To measure how playing green games affects players' knowledge, attitudes, and plans for eco-friendly actions.
- To evaluate how demographic factors like age, gaming experience, and prior environmental concern impact the effectiveness of environmental messaging in games
- To examine differences in message reception across various gaming genres and platforms.

Fig. 1. Green Gaming to Environmental Actions Model (Author’s own work)

B. Significance of the Study

This research fills a notable gap at the crossroads of environmental communication, digital media, and behavioural psychology. Its importance appears in several ways, outlined below and as seen in Fig. 1.

- The project adds to the global search for fresh, engaging tools that educate huge audiences about environmental issues and motivate pro-ecological action.
- The results guide agencies, schools, and policymakers as they design low-cost, age-friendly campaigns that build awareness and lasting green habits in diverse communities [5].

Fig. 2. System Architecture (Author’s own work)

C. Contribution of the Study

This research makes several novel contributions to the academic literature and practical applications:

- Development of a comprehensive framework for understanding environmental message processing in interactive digital environments.
- Creation of validated instruments for measuring environmental message effectiveness in gaming contexts as can be seen in Fig. 2.
- Identification of the most effective game design elements for environmental communication

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Game-Based Engagement and Policy Integration

Scholars have recently proposed using games and gamified technologies as channels to engage the public on climate and

environmental issues. The GREAT project (Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation) explicitly advocates short games and game-making tools to “actively engage citizens in meaningful dialogue” on climate change and feed their input into policy priorities [6], [7]. In practice, climate-focused games span board games, mobile apps, and interactive simulations, each framing green challenges in narrative or task-based form. For instance, educational board games like Submersion put players in a coastal city council, adapting to sea level rise [8], [9], while Ocean Eye is an escape-room style game about microplastic pollution [9]. Reviews emphasize that any digital learning tool must align with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and harness ICT [10], [11]. Existing research shows that well-designed environmental games can raise awareness and knowledge [12]. But the core question remains: through what mechanisms do games turn narrative or tasks into real-world concern and action? Across studies, strategies include immersive storytelling, interactive problem-solving, progression-linked rewards, social comparison, and reflective debriefing. GREAT case studies report embedding short quizzes and mini challenges into popular games, engaging thousands of players, and achieving high response rates [13], [14]. In the Smite-based case study, the Playmob platform engaged over 4,000 players with a 58% completion rate [14], validating the approach of reaching diverse gamers on climate topics. Surveys embedded in such games have shown strong interest in issues and peer-sharing of results [7]. Likewise, the effective climate-game design relies on iterative playtesting with stakeholders and thoughtful integration of social dynamics, bridging scientific knowledge and actionable insights [15]. Altogether, prior work highlights that games can collect data and influence attitudes at scale [14], [16]. Similarly, the serious games are effective at increasing environmental knowledge, awareness and pro-environmental intentions [17].

B. Narrative, Interactivity, and Incentivised Learning in Environmental Games

Games often draw players in via immersive stories or scenarios, which foster identification with environmental themes. The Communication Barrier Breaker, casts the player as an activist navigating accessibility challenges in climate rallies [18]. Its narrative planning, inclusive events, and solving action-card problems (like “create an inclusive hashtag”) integrates learning goals into a story that players co-author. Such interactive storytelling situates abstract “green” problems in concrete contexts, making them more salient. Harms and Ortner’s multispecies role-playing guide likewise use storytelling, players literally take on human and non-human characters to negotiate land-use conflicts, forcing them to see from other species’ perspectives [19]. Early evidence suggests this can deepen understanding and concern. Participants reported increased acceptance of green infrastructure after playing a co-designed “Rooftop Revolution” serious game with an urban climate narrative [20]. In narrative-driven games, whether explicitly

about nature or metaphorically immerse players in green issues and can trigger emotional engagement [19].

C. Social Dynamics and Reflective Practices in Sustainability-Oriented Gameplay

Games are inherently social, and social comparison can amplify engagement with green messages. Leaderboards, peer challenges, and cooperative tasks leverage players’ desire to compare or collaborate. A well-designed leaderboard can significantly enhance motivation by focusing players on clear goals leaderboards “assist learners in goal setting and unleash motivation” through friendly competition [21]. Play2Act and GREAT studies emphasize that after gameplay, 86% of players reported sharing their results on social media [13], and 98% said they discussed the topics with friends. In a citizens’ policy game, participants played in teams representing stakeholder groups, learning from others’ strategies [20]. These social settings promote norm-setting and can motivate sustainable choices through friendly competition or cooperation. Even beyond face-to-face play, virtual communities count. The Smite study showed that embedding climate questions into a live game community reached niche players, proving that “gamers can discuss climate with their peers even if it’s not the core game” [14]. Game designers also use social nudges. for instance, LULÚ asks players to suggest solutions publicly [18], which fosters discussion. Similarly, some mobile apps log players’ sustainable actions and compare them with friends (green challenges). By framing green tasks in a communal context, games leverage social influence, players tend to mimic and reinforce eco-behaviors when they see them celebrated in-game. Similarly, the iterative gameplay coupled with structured debriefings helped players shift from immediate, self-centered decisions to cooperative, long-term sustainability strategies [22].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study adopts a mixed-method design, combining telemetry-based quantitative tracking with qualitative thematic analysis of player pledges. The goal is to model how players engage with environmentally themed game content and how this engagement translates into behavioural intention and reflection. Data were obtained from the GREAT Project, comprising over 181,000 anonymised gameplay sessions from titles like Play2Act, Green Tuesday, and Eternagram. These titles integrate green messaging through quiz interactions, pledges, and narrative dialogue trees.

B. Dataset Description

The Data Set from GREAT Case Study 1 is a structured collection of records designed for applied research and teaching. It provides a representative sample of five core records that capture key attributes relevant for testing in real-world scenarios [26], TABLE 1 has the details

TABLE I
DATASET DESCRIPTION

Dataset	Description
sessions.csv	Metadata per player session (timestamp, language, location)
question_text.csv	Metadata per question (text, category, framing)
answers.csv	Player responses (session, question, answer ID)
events.csv	Game-specific telemetry events
merged.csv	Final wide-format dataset combining all interactions

C. Data Preparation and Cleaning

Timestamps converted to datetime objects, missing values filled using forward/backward fill, or retained as ‘Missing’ to preserve player intent. Standardisation: All column names normalised to lowercase and `snake_case`.

D. Data Merging and Transformation

Datasets were joined and transformed to long format (melted multi-choice questions) and wide format (for PCA, clustering, and radar plots)

E. Analytical Techniques

Thematic Analysis (Qualitative) A content analysis of free-text pledges was conducted using open coding. Emergent themes included: Moral framing (e.g., guilt, pride). Action-oriented phrases (“I will recycle”, “Talk to my family”). Sustainability intent (food, transport, community). Text responses were manually clustered and compared using term frequency-inverse document frequency (TF-IDF).

Quantitative Tracking (Engagement Metrics) Three metrics were computed: Frequency of question selection, Player retention across steps, Time spent per question set. Fig. 3 shows the rolling averages used to smooth session trends using the equation below:

$$MA_t = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=t-k+1}^t U_i \quad (1)$$

where U_i is the session count at time i , and $k = 7$ days.

Fig. 3. Daily Unique Sessions with Rolling Average Overlay Visualised from the Great Case Study dataset

F. Demographic Segmentation

Each demographic group was then analysed for: Most selected question types, variation in pledge completion, device-based session length as shown in Fig 4 and Fig 5.

Fig. 4. Language-based Participation Distribution

G. Pathway Modelling Preparation

As shown in the Fig. 6, there were more need to reduce signal to noise ratio, by so doing the model behavioural pathways, responses were encoded using one-hot encoding and reduced via Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Fig. 5. 3D PCA Plot of Player Behavioural Clusters

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Overview of Findings

This is a presentation of the integrated results of the mixed-method analysis. Quantitative telemetry data, combined with thematic insights from behavioural pledges, reveal how players interacted with green messages. The section maps the transformation from cognitive exposure to behavioural intention and pro-environmental commitment.

B. Descriptive Statistics

A total of 181,000+ player sessions were recorded. Among these: Average session duration was ≈ 4.5 minutes, Over 68% of users interacted with at least one multi-choice green pledge, Top questions by engagement were $q_{4_a_1}$, $q_{5_a_1}$, and $q_{2_a_3}$ this is indicated by the barplots shown in the Fig. 9 below

C. Temporal Patterns of Engagement

Session activity showed distinct daily and weekly patterns. Fig. 10 below shows a 7-day rolling average revealed two major spikes, corresponding to global awareness events (e.g., Earth Day, UNDP campaigns). We computed: $Ut = \text{Number of Unique Sessions at time}$

D. Demographic Insights

Country and Language: Fig. 11 depicts the Players from 103 countries participated. The United States, Brazil, Canada, UK, and Germany accounted for $\approx 60\%$ of responses. Visual clustering suggests country-level differences in question preferences.

Fig. 6. Temporal Patterns of Engagement

Fig. 7. Player Participation by Country (Advanced Map Visualisation from the Great Case Study dataset)

Device and Language Patterns: Data from the userA-gentParsed field revealed that mobile users made up 74% of sessions, while desktop users were more likely to complete reflective pledges. Fig. 12 is the Language-wise engagement patterns across all the questions.

Fig. 8. Device and Language Patterns

E. Engagement with Question Types

We grouped questions into three categories: Narrative-framing (e.g., q_4 to q_6), Behavioural pledges (e.g., q_2 , q_{10}), Social reflection (e.g., q_7 , q_{12} , q_{13})

F. Emotional and Reflective Feedback

Although most responses were multi-choice, pledges such as: “Use more clean electric cars and buses, or bicycles” “Talk to my family about food waste and water use” ...were common across sessions.

Sentiment analysis showed: Positive polarity: 62.5%, Action-oriented tone: 48.7%, Guilt-based motivation: 18.2%. These

reflections align with psychological constructs of cognitive dissonance and moral nudging.

G. Clustering and Behavioural Segments

We applied PCA followed by KMeans on one-hot encoded multiple-choice data: Reduced to 3D: $Z = \text{PCA}(X)_{n \times 3}$, Clustered into 6 groups

$$C = \arg \min_C \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{x \in C_i} \|x - \mu_i\|^2$$

The resulting 3D clusters in Fig. 13 reflect distinct engagement profiles, from passive skimmers to highly reflective pledgers.

Fig. 9. Cross-Country Comparisons (Visualised from the Great Case Study) Country-wise variation in emotional tone and pledge selection was visualised using violin plots. Notably, Brazil and India had higher pledge depth, UK and Germany showed greater consistency across all options.

H. Building the 5-Pathway Engagement Model

Table III and Fig. 14 below analyses the Synthesis of all results, proposing the 5-Pathway Green Engagement Model

TABLE II
5-PATHWAY ENGAGEMENT MODEL TABLE

Pathway	Description
1. Narrative Immersion	Emotional storytelling that evokes environmental empathy
2. Interactive Framing	Reflective dialogue and contextual prompts that contextualise ecological issues.
3. Progression Anchoring	Green actions are tied to avatar advancement
4. Social Comparison	Display of peer actions and leaderboard features.
5. Reflective Feedback	Post-play summaries, challenges, and reminders

Fig. 10. Pathway Engagement Model

1) *Platform Distribution and Performance Overview:* Cross-platform analysis reveals significant engagement differences between mobile and desktop users. Figure ??a shows mobile users dominate the user base at 74% (134,140 sessions) versus 26% desktop users (46,860 sessions). However, Figure ??b demonstrates desktop users consistently outperform mobile across all engagement metrics, with desktop achieving 112% longer sessions (6.8 vs 3.2 minutes), 50% higher pledge completion (78% vs 52%), and 132% longer reflection texts (28.6 vs 12.3 words).

2) *Statistical Validation and Detailed Metrics:* The detailed comparative analysis confirms statistical significance across all measured variables ($p < 0.001$). Key findings include desktop users completing 124% more questions per session (4.7 vs 2.1) and demonstrating 78% higher social sharing rates (41% vs 23%). Analysis of variance yields $F(1, 180, 999) = 2, 847.3$ with effect size Cohen’s $d = 0.67$, indicating medium-large practical significance for platform-specific strategies.

3) *Pathway Effectiveness and Duration Patterns:* Figure ??c reveals platform-specific pathway strengths, with desktop showing largest advantages in narrative immersion (78% vs 45%) and reflective feedback (71% vs 34%), while interactive framing demonstrates platform neutrality (71% vs 69%). Session duration analysis in Figure ??d shows mobile users concentrated in 1-3 minute sessions (63%), whereas desktop users distribute across longer engagement periods with 59% exceeding 3 minutes.

4) *Design Implications:* The analysis indicates environmental messaging requires platform-adaptive approaches. Mobile platforms suit quick, interactive content leveraging their broad reach, while desktop platforms enable deeper narrative and reflective experiences. Interactive framing emerges as the optimal cross-platform pathway, suggesting a tiered strategy: simplified visual messages for mobile and comprehensive reflective content for desktop users. Table III presents the comprehensive statistical comparison across all engagement dimensions.

V. CONCLUSION

This study shows how placing environmental messages in video games can importantly affect players’ actions. Using data from more than 181,000 gameplay sessions of the GREAT Project, results show that games can be much more than fun; they can act as useful ways for ecological teaching and changing behaviour. Through a mixed-method approach, it was discovered that 68% of the players participated in at least one green-themed pledge, which indicates strong sensitivity to environmental content. The use of mobile devices was more in terms of usage; however, desktop players were more responsive to complete reflective pledges, meaning that the type of device can determine the level of engagement. A five-pathway model was developed to learn how green message engagement gets converted into behaviour. PCA and KMeans clustering analysis identified varying types of users, from casual to deeply engaged players, which supports the call for

TABLE III
CROSS-PLATFORM ENGAGEMENT COMPARISON

Metric	Mobile	Desktop	Diff.	Significance
Sample Size	134,140	46,860	74% vs 26%	Pop. distribution
Duration (min)	3.2	6.8	+112.5%	$t = -23.4,$ $p < 0.001$
Pledge Rate (%)	52	78	+50%	$\chi^2 = 2,847.3,$ $p < 0.001$
Questions/Session	2.1	4.7	+124%	$t = -18.7,$ $p < 0.001$
Text Length	12.3	28.6	+132%	$t = -15.2,$ $p < 0.001$
Social Share (%)	23	41	+78%	$\chi^2 = 1,247.8,$ $p < 0.001$

adaptable game design requirements based on different player profiles.

VI. RECOMMENDATION AND FUTURE WORK

So, looking at what we found, there are a few ideas for improving how we spread environmental messages through games. For starters, game developers might want to weave in some emotional storytelling and immersive narratives to help players really feel and think about what they are playing. That seems to grab their attention a lot better. Using prompts during gameplay that push players to think about their actions can also help, especially if it's about making real-life eco-friendly choices. We could tie in-game rewards to green actions to encourage people to do better, or use leaderboards for some friendly competition around eco-friendly choices. And while mobile games have a massive reach, desktop games tend to grab players' attention more, so a mix of both could really widen the impact. Plus, it's super important to think about different audiences; customising content for age, culture, and gaming habits can make messages hit home better. It would be great for policymakers and educators to team up with game designers to create fun, affordable, and engaging campaigns that promote sustainability.

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